

lic ring, the chalcone analogues or the 3-cinnamoyl naphthapyridinone derivatives (IV a-e) were prepared by the Claisen-Schmidt condensation of an appropriate aldehyde with the methyl ketones (IIa, b) using ethanol as a solvent and potassium hydroxide as base^{6,7}.

The infrared spectra of the 3-cinnamoyl naphthapyridinones (IV) showed well defined absorption bands attributable to the carbonyl group (1700 cm^{-1}), the hydroxyl group (3030 cm^{-1}) and for the C=N group (1620 cm^{-1}).

With a view to studying some of the reactions of the chalcone analogues (IV), they were allowed to react with hydrazine or phenyl hydrazine giving pyrazolines.

This reaction has now been extended to (IV a, b, e). The reaction with hydrazine in ethanol yields the corresponding hydrazones which rearrange immediately to the isomeric 3(5-aryl-2-pyrazolin-3-yl)-4-aryl-5, 6-dihydro-naphtha(2, 1-e) 2(1H) pyridinones (Va-c). However, the reaction of hydrazine with the chalcone (IVa) in acetic acid led to the for-

mation of 3-(1-acetyl-5-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-3-yl)-4-phenyl-5, 6-dihydro-naphtha(2, 1-e) 2(1H)-pyridinones (Vg). When pyrazoline derivative (Va) was heated under reflux in acetic acid and in the presence of freshly fused sodium acetate, (Vg) was readily obtained.

The action of phenyl hydrazine on the chalcones (IV,a,b,c) and 3-(1,5-diaryl-2-pyrazolin-3-yl)-4-aryl-5, 6-dihydro naphtha(2, 1-e) 2(1H) pyridinones (Vd-f) obtained.

The above pyrazoline products (Va-g) give the colour test for pyrazolines (a drop of ferric chloride solution added to a concentrated sulphuric acid solution of the compound gives a blue-violet colour).

The i.r. measurements of the products (Va-f) showed stretching frequencies at 1630 cm^{-1} , 1660 cm^{-1} , and 3030 cm^{-1} characteristic for C=N-, amide (CO), and the NH group respectively.

Experimental

Analytical data were determined in the micro-analytical unit, Cairo University. Infrared spectra were recorded on a SP1000 Pye-Unicam spectrophotometer.

3-Acyl-4-aryl-5, 6-dihydro-naphtha (2, 1-e) 2(1H) pyridinones (IIa-d)

To a suspension of (Ia, b) (2.0g in each case in dry benzene (50 ml) was added dropwise an ethereal solution of methylmagnesium iodide or phenylmagnesium bromide prepared from magnesium (0.9 g), methyl iodide (7.0 g) or bromobenzene, (8.0 g) and dry ether (40 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed

for 3 hr., set aside at room temperature, and then decomposed with a cold 10% HCl solution.

The yellow solid obtained was crystallized from acetic acid to give the 3-acyl-4-aryl-5, 6-dihydro-naphtha (2, 1-e)2(1H)-pyridinones (IIa-d). (c.f. Table 1).

Action of hydrazine hydrate on 3-Cinnamoyl-naphthapyridinones (IV a, b, e) :

(a) *In ethanol :*

To a solution of the chalcone analogues (IV a, b, e) (1 g. in each case) in ethanol (20 ml), hydrazine hydrate (50 % , 2 ml) was added and the mixture

TABLE 1. 3-ACYL-4-ARYL-5, 6-DIHYDRO-NAPHTHA(2, 1-e)2(1H) PYRIDINONES(IIa-d).

Compound	m.p. °C	Yield (%)	Formula	Analysis					
				Found (%)		Required			
			C	H	N	C	H	N	
IIa	295	85	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ NO ₂	80.2	5.5	4.4	80.0	5.39	4.44
IIb	278	82	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ NO ₂	76.3	5.6	4.0	76.52	5.50	4.05
IIc	above 310	80	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ NO ₂	82.8	5.3	3.6	82.75	5.04	3.71
IId	above 310	77	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ NO ₂	79.5	5.1	3.4	79.60	5.15	3.43

Action of hydrazines on 3-acylnaphthapyridinone derivatives (IIa-c).

A mixture of the 3-acyl naphthapyridinones (IIa-c) (0.5 g. in each case), hydrazine hydrate and/or phenyl hydrazine (0.5 ml), and ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and the precipitated solid was collected by filtration. Recrystallization of the product obtained from acetic acid gave the corresponding hydrazones (IIIa-f) as yellow crystals (cf. Table 2).

refluxed for 5 hr. The solid that separated upon concentrating the reaction mixture was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol to give the 3-(5-aryl-2-pyrazolin-3-yl)-4-aryl-5, 6-dihydro-naphtha (2, 1-e) 2 (1H) pyridinones (Va-c) as yellow crystals. (c.f. Table 4).

(b) *In acetic acid :*

A mixture of the chalcone IVa (1g), hydrazine hydrate (50% ; 8 ml) and acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 5 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and the precipitated solid was collected by filtration.

TABLE 2. 3-ACYL NAPHTHAPYRIDINONE HYDRAZONES (IIIa-f)

Compound	m.p. °C	Yield (%)	Formula	Analysis				Required (%)	
				Found (%)		Required (%)			
			C	H	N	C	H	N	
IIIa	315	90	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	76.7	5.7	12.8	76.6	5.7	12.7
IIIb	310	87	C ₂₇ H ₂₅ N ₃ O	80.4	5.6	10.3	80.0	5.6	10.3
IIIc	260	90	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂	73.4	5.1	11.6	73.5	5.2	11.5
IIId	291	89	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂	77.2	5.7	9.6	77.2	5.7	9.5
IIIe	248	85	C ₂₆ H ₂₇ N ₃ O	79.7	5.4	10.8	79.8	5.4	10.8
IIIf	297	82	C ₂₈ H ₂₅ N ₃ O	82.1	5.4	8.9	82.2	5.3	8.9

Condensation of 3-acetyl-4-aryl-5, 6-dihydro-naphtha (2, 1-e) 2(1H)pyridinones(IIIa, b) with aldehydes.

To a solution of (IIa, b) (0.02 mol) in alcoholic potassium hydroxide, appropriate aldehydes was added (0.02 mol) and the reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature. The solid obtained upon dilution of the reaction mixture with water was filtered and recrystallized from acetic acid to give (IV a-e) as yellow crystals. (cf. Table 3).

Recrystallization of the product from acetic acid gave the 3-(N-acetyl pyrazolinyl) naphtha pyridinones (Vg) as yellow crystals (c.f. table 4).

Conversion of (Va) to (Vg)

3-pyrazolinyl-naphthapyridones (Va) (1 g), was heated under reflux in acetic acid (25 ml), containing freshly fused sodium acetate (0.2 g), for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and the precipitated

TABLE 3. 3-CINNAMOYL-NAPHTHAPYRIDINONES (IVa-e)

Compound	m.p. °C	Yield (%)	Formula	Analysis				Required (%)	
				Found (%)		Required (%)			
			C	H	N	C	H	N	
IVa	269	81	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ NO ₂	83.1	5.2	3.4	83.3	5.2	3.4
IVb	277	83	C ₂₉ H ₂₃ NO ₂	80.3	5.4	3.2	80.3	5.3	3.2
IVc	258	80	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	75.0	4.2	6.2	75.0	4.4	6.2
IVd	185	75	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ NO ₂	83.7	5.1	3.1	83.9	5.3	3.2
IVe	265	83	C ₂₉ H ₂₃ NO ₂	80.4	5.3	3.1	80.3	5.3	3.2

TABLE 4. 3-PYRAZOLINYL-NAPATHA PYRIDINONES (Va-g)

Compound	m.p. °C	Yield (%)	Formula	Analysis				Required (%)	
				Found (%)				H	N
Va	245	85	C ₂₈ H ₂₃ N ₃ O	80.6	5.4	10.2	80.5	5.5	10.1
Vb	256	87	C ₂₉ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂	77.8	5.5	10.3	77.8	5.6	9.4
Vc	260	83	C ₂₉ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	77.6	5.5	9.4	77.8	5.6	9.4
Vd	242	80	C ₃₄ H ₂₇ N ₃ O	82.5	5.3	8.5	82.7	5.5	8.5
Ve	288	85	C ₃₂ H ₂₆ N ₃ O	80.3	5.5	8.3	80.3	5.5	8.3
Vf	290	80	C ₂₈ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	80.3	5.5	8.2	80.3	5.5	8.3
Vg	299	81	C ₃₀ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₂	78.2	5.3	9.2	78.4	5.4	9.1

solid was collected by filtration. Recrystallization of the product from acetic acid gave the 3-(N-acetyl pyrazolinyl) derivatives (Vg) m.p. and mixed m.p. 299°.

Action of phenylhydrazine on 3-Cinnamoyl naphthapyridones (IV a, b and e).

A mixture of (IV a, b and e) (1g in each case), phenylhydrazine (0.5 ml), and acetic acid (20 ml) was refluxed for 5 hr., cooled and the orange crystals which separated were recrystallized from acetic acid to give 3-pyrazolinyl naphthapyridinones (V d-f) (cf. Table 4).

References

1. T. ZIMAITY, A. M. KHALIL, I. I. ABD EL GAWAD and S. FOUDA ; work under publication.
2. R. L. SCHRINER, and T. A. TURNER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 1267.
3. R. L., FRANK, and C. WEATHERBEE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3482.
4. A., SAMMOUR, Y. AKHNOOKH, and H. JAHINE, *U.A.R., J. Chem.*, 1971, 14 (3), 213.
5. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", JOHN WILEY and SONS, N. Y. 1959 p. 214.
6. N.S. VULFSON, and G. M. SUKHOTINA, *Kim Geterotsiki Scand.*, 1967 ; 682, *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, 68, 39432.
7. M., CASSAC, and A., BOUCHERLE, *Chim. Ther.*, 1967 ; 2, 101 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, 68, 21799.
8. V. KNORR, *Ann.*, 1887, 238, 200.